

Zooplankton diversity in certain ponds of Cuddalore District of Tamilnadu, India

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ABSTRACT

A study on zooplankton species diversity in 5 fresh water ponds of Cuddalore district, Tamil Nadu, India. The plankton samples were collected (January, 2009 - June, 2009) from 5 different fresh water ponds. Zooplankton invariably forms an integral component of freshwater communities and contributes significantly to biological productivity. It is form an important food component for various aquatic animals and helps to transfer energy from primary to secondary and tertiary levels in the form of food chain. The freshwater ponds infested with dense growth of aquatic vegetation of various submerged, floating and emergent types, providing diverse habitats for different faunal communities. The identified zooplankton were, Rotifers comprises 9 species (36%), Cladocera -6 (24%), Copepoda -7 (28%) and Ostracoda -3 (12%). In this study, the dominant species were Rotifers and followed by Cladocera. The zooplankton diversity analysis shows an average abundance in winter and maximum occurrence in summer due to the different environmental characteristics of the fresh water body.

Keywords: Zooplankton, diversity, freshwater ponds, Cuddalore district.

INTRODUCTION

Fresh water habitats occupy a relatively small portion living of the earth's surface as compared to marine and terrestrial habitats. As far as man's relationship with fresh water is concerned, the combined effect of population growth, increased standard of living and greater leisure time to make larger demands on available water resources, fresh water has proved to be an essential resource for the development as successful modern societies and a useful means to compare standards of living of different nations to examine the per capita consumption of water. Zooplanktons are the small, floating and weakly swimming animals found in various

water bodies. The zooplankton population of freshwater play vital role in food web of the food chain nutrient recycling and transfer of organic matter from primary producers like diatoms to secondary consumers like fishes. Zooplankton help to determine the quantum of fish stock and the failure of fishery resources is attributed to the reduced Copepod population (Stottrup, 2000 and Tiwari *et al.*, 1991). Species diversity indices of zooplankton communities are used to evaluate the quality of water with respect to industrial, municipal and domestic pollution (Acharjee *et al.*, 1995). Hence zooplankton can be used as an indicator of sorority. In this juncture, studies on the population dynamics of zooplankton with reference to their diversity, density, commonness and energetic are essential for optimizing the

productivity of the system and also for their management practices. The present study envisaged to know the diversity of zooplankton in the freshwater ponds of Cuddalore district.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plankton samples were collected during the early hours of the day in 5 different fresh water ponds of Cuddalore district of Tamil Nadu, India. The samples were collected from January-2009 to June-2009. Samples were collected using a plankton net (30 cm diameter) made up of bottom silt of 50 mm mesh size by towing the plankton net horizontally at a depth of 40 cm for about 10 minutes. These ponds are namely, Kondrchetty pond, Veernar pond, Chatrakulam pond, Malli pond and Aappa pond located Vridhachalamtaluk. The collected samples were filtered with the help of filter to remove the water. The plankton samples were then transferred to a plastic bottle containing 5 % formalin using a camel brush for later microscopic analysis. In the laboratory, the plankton samples were poured into a broad petridish and they were separated into different groups like copepods, cyclopoids, calanoids, cladocerans, rotifers and ostracods under a binocular stereo zoom dissection microscope using a fine pointed painting brush and a needle.

For quantitative and qualitative analysis, 100 liters of water was drawn from each of the fresh water ponds at a depth of 2 feet and filtered through the plankton net. The planktons were carefully transferred into a plastic bottle without any loss and preserved in 5% neutral formalin. The sample was diluted to 10 ml using neutral formalin. The diluted samples were thoroughly mixed and 1 ml of the sample was pipette out into the Sedgewick-Rafter counting chamber using a wide mouthed pipette for the enumeration. The enumeration was done for 10 ml and the average was taken. The Sedgewick-Rafter counting chamber consists of 100 squares. The number and the type of zooplankton in each square were counted and added to account the number of zooplankton presents in 1 ml of the sample. The number of zooplankton in 1 ml represents organisms per litre of the freshwater

for larger zooplankton. The zooplanktons were counted under a compound microscope and each species was recorded. Enumeration was carried out in the samples and mean was calculated the number of zooplankton per litre was calculated using the following formula (Santhanamet al., 1989).

$$N = nxv/V$$

Where

N = Total number of plankton in 1 litre of water filtered

N = Average number of plankton in 1 ml of plankton sample

v = Volume of plankton concentrated (1 ml)

V = Volume of total water filtered (litre)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The zooplankton of fresh water bodies constitutes an extremely diverse assemblage of organisms mostly represented by invertebrate Phyla. They constitute an important link between primary producers and consumers of higher order in aquatic food web. In the present study, an attempt was made to analyses the zooplanktonic composition of 5 different freshwater ponds of Cuddalore district from January- 2009 to June- 2009. The qualitative studies on the zooplankton population of all ponds showed 25 species of zooplankton belonging to Copepods, Cladocera, Rotifera and Ostracods were identified in the present study (Table-1)

Table - 1: This table show the Zooplanktons identified in the fresh water bodies of Cuddalore district, Tamil Nadu

S. No.	Groups	Species
1	Rotifers	<i>Brachinouscaudatus</i> <i>Brachionusbidentatus</i> <i>Brachionusdiversicornis</i> <i>Brachionuscalyciflorus</i> <i>Brachionusbforficula</i> <i>Brachionusrubens</i> <i>Brachionusangularis</i> <i>Brachinousfalcatatus</i> <i>Keratellatropica</i>
2	Cladocera	<i>Ceriodaphniacornuta</i>

		<i>Diaphanasomasarsi</i>
		<i>Diaphanosomacarinata</i>
		<i>Alonaverrucosa</i>
		<i>Alona rectangular</i>
		<i>Macrothrixlaticornis</i>
3	Copepoda	<i>Heliodiaptomusviduus</i>
		<i>Sinodiaptomusindicus</i>
		<i>Mesocyclopscyclopoides</i>
		<i>Mesocyclopsaspericornis</i>
		<i>Mesocyclopsshyalinus</i>
		<i>Nauplius sp.</i>
		<i>Copepodid sp.</i>
4	Ostrocooda	<i>Hemicyprisfossulate</i>
		<i>Stenocypris sp.</i>
		<i>Cypris sp.</i>

Among these zooplankton, Cyclopoid, Copepods occurred commonly whereas Cladoceran, Calanoid, Copepods and Rotifers were recorded less frequently. Wilhm and Dorris (1968) suggested that the increase in diversity is an indication of the healthier environmental condition and low diversity suggested fewer species dominance probably due to sewage environmental stress.

The quantitative analysis of zooplankton was carried out in the Kondrachetty pond, Veernar pond, Chatra pond, Malli pond and Aappa pond (Table -2). Zooplankton density of these ponds indicated variation in different ponds. Low density, moderate density and high density of the zooplankton in these ponds can be correlated to high, moderate and low pollution in these ponds.

higher pollution and improper maintenance. The higher pollution due to domestic sewage, industrial pollutants and agricultural pollutants affect the water quality and diversity of the zooplankton. Hence there should be some remedial measures to prevent release of these pollutants to these ponds, so that the native condition of these ponds can be restored. High diversity of the zooplankton was recorded mainly in Aappa pond and Kondrachetty pond. These ponds are well maintained with normal ecological condition. These ponds have clear water due to least pollution. The chemical parameters of these ponds appear to be optimum and there is proper recirculation of nutrients leading to production of ecologically balanced food chains and food webs. These might be the reasons for occurrence of different species of Copepods, Cladocerans, Rotifers and Ostracods. Due to protected conditions, these ponds showed higher diversity of zooplankton. Further maintenance of the water quality supports production of many commercially important fishes. Additionally many of these ponds form important source of drinking water and irrigate agricultural fields. Hence the present study suggested protecting the fresh water ponds in order to maintain their normal ecology and to get many benefits from them.

CONCLUSION

In the present study, an attempt has been made to

Table - 2: These tables show the density of Zooplankton (Mean±SE) of five fresh water bodies (No/M³)

Zooplankton	Kondrachetty pond	Veernar pond	Chatra pond	Malli pond	Aappa pond
Calanoid Male	867±133	500±115	300±58	267±33	500±100
Calanoid Female	4000±721	1833±176	2767±240	500±58	7000v1852
Calanoid ovigerous	--	167±133	--	167±33	500±100
Cyclopoid Male	933±133	700±58	500±115	467±176	700±100
Cyclopoid Female	5400±503	3833±578	2633±255	267±107	7900±557
Cyclopoid ovigerous	--	200±58	--	--	--
Cladocerans	4200±917	--	--	--	1000±200
Rotifers	167±67	--	33±33	100±100	3600±293
Ostrocoods	--	233±33	--	1067±133	67±67
Total	15567±2474	7466±1071		2835±640	21267±3269

from January-2009 to June-2009. In this study, 25 species of zooplankton belonging to Copepods, Cladocerans, Rotifera and Ostracods were identified. Cyclopoid copepods occurred commonly in all freshwater ponds studied. Cladoceran, Calanoid Copepods and Rotifers were recorded less frequently. Quantitative analysis of zooplankton was carried out in the Kondrchetty pond, Veernar pond, Chatra pond, Malli pond and Aappa pond. Density of zooplankton of these ponds indicated variation in different ponds. Low density, moderate density and high density of the zooplankton in these ponds can be correlated to high, moderate and low pollution in these ponds. Results indicate high productivity of zooplankton and fishes in well protected ponds such as Kondrchetty pond, Chatra pond and Malli ponds. Domestic sewage, agricultural pesticides and anthropogenic activities polluted the ponds result in poor diversity and density of zooplankton. Remedial measures have to be taken to prevent further degradation of these fresh water ponds.

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